

4. SVETOVNI DAN VARNOSTI HRANE 2022

4th WORLD FOOD SAFETY DAY 2022

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Državni svet Republike Slovenije
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UPRAVA RS ZA VARNO HRANO,
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4. Svetovni dan varnosti hrane 2022
4th World Food Safety Day 2022

Varnejša hrana, boljše zdravje
Safer food, better health

Izbral in uredil / Selected and edited by
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Sprejemanje odločitev v sistemu EFSA – pasti in rešitve

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Ključne besede: varnost hrane, ocena tveganja, upravljanje s tveganji.

Evropska agencija za varno hrano (EFSA) s sedežem v Parmi v Italiji je ena od več kot 40 evropskih agencij, ki so ustanovljene predvsem z namenom svetovati Evropski komisiji, Evropskemu parlamentu, Evropskemu svetu in državam članicam EU pri sprejemanju pomembnih odločitev na najrazličnejših področjih, pomembnih za EU, kot tudi širše. Poslanstvo EFSA vključuje izredno široko področje prehranjevalne verige in okolja z neposrednim ali posrednim vplivom na varnost hrane in krme, vključno z zdravjem in dobrim počutjem živali, varstvom rastlin ter zdravjem in prehrano rastlin, kot tudi okolja. Pri tem je vloga EFSA vseh 20 let njenega delovanja predvsem informirati politične odločevalce z neodvisnimi strokovnimi mnenji, ocenami in tveganji, ki temeljijo na najboljši možni znanstveni osnovi. Sprejemanje odločitev glede teh mnenj na ravni EU in posameznih držav članic pa je vloga politikov. Trenutna evropska zakonodaja določa, da so podjetja oziroma prijavitelji, ki želijo odobritev novega izdelka, odgovorna za izdelavo študij, ki strokovnjakom omogočajo ustrezen pregled in oceno njihove varnosti. Natančno predpisane so tudi vrste študij in metode, ki ne morejo biti pripravljene glede na želje in pričakovanja prijaviteljev. Ta pristop velja npr. v EU za fitofarmacevtska sredstva že od leta 2009. Tako EFSA kot večina strokovne javnosti na tem področju menita, da je to primeren, pregleden in objektivni postopek. Kljub temu EFSA občasno pristopi k izdelavi lastnih izračunov in ocen tveganja z uporabo surovih, neobdelanih podatkov. To ni zgolj v primeru prehranskih izdelkov, takšen pristop uporablja med drugim tudi Evropska agencija za zdravila (EMA) v primeru zdravil. EFSA pri svojem delu ves čas svojega delovanja poskuša v največji meri slediti vrednotam, kot so znanstvena odličnost, neodvisnost oziroma nepristranskost strokovnjakov in drugega osebja, spodbujanje kulture odprtosti in dostopnosti, odgovornost, inovativnost in sodelovanje v širšem smislu. Te vrednote so tudi pomemben del zadnjega strateškega dokumenta EFSA (EFSA Strategy 2027), ki je bil sprejet junija 2021. V tem dokumentu so ob ciljih za naslednje srednjeročno obdobje še posebej izpostavljeni izzivi, s katerimi se EFSA spopada že dlje časa oziroma vsaj zadnjih 10 let in ostajajo tudi v prihodnje v marsičem enaki – od vprašanj glede neodvisnosti, objektivnosti in preprečevanja konflikta interesov pri sodelujočih strokovnjakih in zaposlenih, boljšega sodelovanja z različnimi deležniki, predvsem nevladnimi organizacijami, večje

neodvisnosti od že pripravljenih študij industrije kot podlaga za izdelavo ocen tveganj, večje odprtosti oziroma dostopnosti podatkov podjetij v procesu ocenjevanja, večje upoštevanje rezultatov raziskav izven predpisanega sistema ocenjevanja, boljše komuniciranje in sodelovanje s širšo javnostjo in mediji, boljše sodelovanje z državami članicami pri zagotavljanju ustreznih strokovnjakov za delo v znanstvenem odboru, znanstvenih panelih in različnih delovnih skupinah, s čimer bi zagotovili znanstveno strokovno znanje in tako izboljšali učinkovitost svojega dela. EFSA je pogosto tudi vmesnik oziroma prevajalec med znanstvenim sektorjem, javnostjo, vključno z nevladnimi organizacijami, in oblikovalci politik. Na žalost pogosto kljub vrednotam, kot so znanstvena odličnost in visoki standardi neodvisnosti, del politike in javnosti niso vedno zadovoljni z odločitvami EFSA. Skrb vzbujajo dejstva, da oblikovalci politik danes pogosto dajejo prednost javnemu mnenju, namesto da bi podprli znanstveno podprte odločitve svojih agencij, ki so jim ne nazadnje sami postavili pravila, na podlagi katerih delujejo. K temu prispevajo tudi javni mediji, ki neredko zaradi težnje po uravnoteženju informacij, za in proti, ne glede na kakovost in izvor informacij, primerjajo znanstveno vprašljive in nepreverjene podatke s strokovno in znanstveno utemeljenimi mnenji, kar posledično največkrat vodi v napačne in v medijih dobro sprejete domneve. Rad bi poudaril, da so za Slovenijo teme, ki jih pokriva EFSA, zelo pomembne. Vemo, da je varnost hrane in krme z ekologijo temeljna naloga in obveznost vsake države. Vemo tudi, da te teme niso več izključno notranja zadeva posameznih držav. Številne težave in tveganja na tem zelo širokem področju so globalni, zato zahtevajo regionalni, evropski in globalni pristop ter intenzivno sodelovanje. Zaradi teh razlogov bi v Sloveniji morali biti veseli, da smo del tega sistema in da z njim čim boljše sodelujemo po svojih zmožnostih. Zagotavljanje neodvisnih znanstvenih mnenj in ocen tveganja seveda ne bi bilo mogoče brez številnih odličnih strokovnjakov iz vseh držav EU in širše, podprtih z visoko strokovnim osebjem EFSA. Pri tem bi morala tudi Slovenija prispevati več kot zdaj, saj je bil v letu 2018 v postopku izbora strokovnjakov za obnovo članov Znanstvenih panelov in Znanstvenega odbora med 174 izbranimi zgolj eden iz Slovenije. Na podlagi svojih štiriletnih izkušenj kot član Upravnega odbora EFSA in 20-letnega spremljanja dela EFSA sem globoko prepričan, da EFSA svoje delo opravlja profesionalno, nepristransko in učinkovito. Glede na to, da sem že vrsto let vpet v delovanje različnih institucij, tako vladnih kot nevladnih, na področju kmetijstva in okolja v Sloveniji, lahko z veliko mero trdim, da pri nas tako odlično vodene, organizirane in po delovanju strokovne, pregledne in neodvisne institucije ne poznam.

EFSA system decision making – setups and solutions

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The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), based in Parma, Italy, is one of more than 40 European agencies established primarily to advise the EU Commission, the EU Parliament, the EU Council, and the EU Member States on important decisions in a variety of areas that are important for the EU as well as for a broader area. The mission of EFSA encompasses an extremely broad area of the food chain and the environment that has a direct or indirect impact on food and feed safety, including animal health and welfare, plant protection, plant health and nutrition, and the environment. EFSA's role has been to inform policymakers through independent expert opinions, assessments, and risks based on the best scientific grounds possible over the course of its 20-year existence. Politicians, however, are responsible for making decisions on these opinions at the EU and individual Member State levels. According to current EU legislation, companies or applicants wishing to get a new product approved are responsible for conducting all studies that allow experts to properly review and assess its safety. All kinds of studies and methods are also precisely and mandatorily defined and cannot be prepared arbitrarily based on the applicants' wishes and expectations. Since 2009, this approach has been valid in the EU for pesticides, for example. Both EFSA and the large majority of other professionals in the field regard this as an appropriate, transparent, and objective process. Nonetheless, the EFSA occasionally approaches its own calculations and risk assessments with the use of raw, unprocessed data. This approach is used not only in the case of food products, but also in the case of medicines by the European Medicines Agency (EMA). Throughout its operations, EFSA has attempted to pursue values such as scientific excellence, independence, or impartiality of all experts and other staff, while also promoting a culture of openness and accessibility, responsibility, innovation, and cooperation in a broader sense. These values are also emphasized in the latest EFSA Strategy 2027 paper, which was adopted in June 2021. In this document besides main objectives for the next medium-term, document especially highlights challenges that EFSA has faced for a long time, or at least for the last ten years, and that have remained the same in many aspects – from issues of independence, objectivity, and conflict of interest prevention among participating experts and employees, better cooperation with various interested parties, particularly NGO's, greater independence from already prepared industry studies as a basis for risk

assessments, greater openness or accessibility of company data in the assessment process, greater consideration of research results outside the prescribed assessment system, improved communication and cooperation with the general public and media, improved cooperation with Member States in providing relevant experts to work in the Scientific Committee, Scientific Panels, and various working groups in order to provide the necessary scientific expertise and thus improve the efficiency of their work. EFSA is often used as a terminal or translator between the scientific community, the general public, as well as NGO's and policymakers. Unfortunately, despite values such as scientific excellence and high standards of independence, parts of the policy and parts of the public are not always satisfied with EFSA's decisions. Worryingly, policymakers today frequently prioritize public opinion over scientifically supported decisions made by their agencies, who have, after all, established the ground rules under which they operate. Due to the tendency to balance information for and against, regardless of quality or source, the public media also contributes by comparing scientifically questionable and unverified data with expert and scientifically-based opinions, which, in most cases, leads to incorrect and widely accepted assumptions in the media. I would like to emphasize that the issues addressed by EFSA are critical to Slovenia. We are all aware that food and feed safety, along with ecology, is a fundamental task and obligation of every country. We also know that these issues are no longer solely the domain of individual countries. Numerous problems and risks exist on a global scale, necessitating a regional, European, and global approach as well as intensive cooperation. For all of these reasons, we in Slovenia should be grateful to be a part of this system and try our best to cooperate with it. Of course, ensuring independent scientific opinions and risk assessments would not be possible without a large number of excellent experts from across the EU and beyond, backed up by EFSA's highly qualified staff. Slovenia should contribute more than it currently does; in fact, only one of the 174 selected experts in the process of selecting experts for the renewal of the Scientific Panels and the Scientific Committee was from Slovenia in 2018. Based on my four years of experience as a member of the EFSA Management Board and nearly 20 years of monitoring EFSA's work, I am convinced that EFSA is performing its duties professionally, impartially, and efficiently. Given that I have been involved in the work of various institutions, both governmental and non-governmental, in the fields of agriculture and the environment in Slovenia for many years, I can say with confidence that I am not aware of any other independent and transparent institution in Slovenia that is so well managed, organized, and professional.